

**IMPLEMENTATION OF
INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY
IN FACULTY OF ISLAMIC EDUCATION
JAKARTA ISLAMIC UNIVERSITY**

Dr. Mulyadi, M.Pd.Ph.D
(mul_amir07@yahoo.com)
Pascasarjana Program
Universitas Islam Jakarta

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to describe the implementation of information communications technology in Faculty of Islamic Education, Jakarta Islamic Universty. This research method is descriptive qualitative research. Data collection techniques using participant observation, interview and documentation. Data analysis procedure performed by the display, reduction, categorisation, syntesis, and hypothesis.

The results of this study are; (1) the application of ICTs backdrop that the concept of people today live in technolog century, then whether they like it or not, humans have to use technology, (2) the process of planning, implementation and evaluation is done through meetings beginning of the curriculum that is integrated in the learning, (3) the process of integrating ICT into the learning activities carried out by providing training for teachers to make a powerpoint, data processing with Microsoft Excel, (4) realizing students minded national and international, (5) ICT be used as a learning tool, administration and as media promotion for institution, (6) the hallmark of ICT in Faculty of Islamic Education, Jakarta Islamic Universty is to optimize the role of ICT, not half-measures for specific needs alone, (7) the constraints on its -implementation is the electric power is still low, is still a deficit of around 50% power and Bottlenext when using Server.

Based on the results, this study offers some recommendations, namely; Faculty of Islamic Education, Jakarta Islamic Universty must immediately address the issue of lack of power, and hold a new Client Server with a larger capacity.

Keywords: Information Communication Technology.

A. Introduction

Information Communication Technology (ICT) has an important role in the development of the educational system. So far the use of ICT in academic level in the university has increased. The internet hold way in global information dissemination of knowledge, In essence, the use of technology in the field of education is a necessity because today the flow of globalization is very strong with the spread of science. This is the importance of applying ICT in learning. It makes easier for teachers in teaching, the use of ICT is also greatly felt by all parties in the university environment where ICT is used.

Based on the results of a preliminary study that the number of students of Faculty Islamic Education have been increasing every year. This affected the students service. New Students certainly have complexity in learning. The faculty provides computers that are not as compatible with the number of students. Similarly, a teacher is required to always improve his quality, both in the development of professional classifications and his pedagogical skills.

In other conditions, the implementation of ICT in learning activities is assumed to have not run optimally. There are several forms of ICT implementation in learning in this regard, such as the use of computers as a medium for student learning, the use of the internet as an open source by students and teachers to develop learning, and the use of local network systems (LANs) can make the command line into one direction / centralistic.

Another problem faced in the implentation of ICT is the uneven distribution of human resources that can operate computers better. Most senior teachers only understand the operation of Microsoft office, but some of them do not understand well about other computer programs such as website design, Corel draw, Photoshop and so on. This requires teachers and other staff to develop skills in computer development. This weakness can hamper the creativity of teachers in achieving learning goals.

The practice of computer-based in learning cannot be carried out instantly. Teachers design learning through the preparation of lesson plans which is followed by making learning media. One problem that is often faced by teachers in this case is when designing media, teachers need other teachers who can help design learning media and integrate it with other learning resources.

As for the implementation of learning, several obstacles that are often faced by teachers include; (1) power failure. This condition is a routine problem because of the unavailability of adequate electricity voltage. (2) LCD is not working well. (3) Wi-Fi networks are not yet turned on or often material files are exposed to viruses and cannot be operated. Such conditions are indeed unpredictable but often become obstacles in carrying out learning.

In learning activities, the existence of sophisticated technology becomes a source, the source of information is no longer focused solely on the text book, but it is wider than that. Now to access learning information, students can use open source, can be through internet media or other forms of computer-based multimedia. On the other hand if this ICT is applied in the field of education, it will have an impact on improving the quality of teaching and learning processes to be more effective and efficient, especially the techniques, approaches, strategies and methods used when learning activities take place, both in the classroom and outside the classroom.

Efforts to implement ICT in learning activities can be seen as a solution to solving current learning problems, especially when viewed from the point of view of the benefits of their use. There are so many benefits that can be obtained through the application of ICT in learning, but it is also very necessary to pay attention to the subjects who can make these efforts, such as education practitioners or learning technologists.

On the other hand, the use of ICT in learning activities, can be one of the important factors that enable the speed of transformation of knowledge to students more broadly. The application of information technology into the world of education has created a great influence. By utilizing the sophistication of information technology, the quality and efficiency of education can be improved. This is as revealed by Geer (2014) that technology plays a key role in how students play, learn, gain information, and interact with others. This opinion expressly states how technology is the way students interact with their friends, obtain information and learn. Students who are in the digital age today tend to more easily access information from various media, so this has an impact on the way they interact and use the information itself.

Based on the description of the background above, the researcher was interested in examining it with the title: "Implementation of Information and Communication Technology in Faculty of Islamic Education, Jakarta Islamic University. This research is a qualitative research. The study was conducted by interviewing Dean, Head of department, teachers and Students who have adequate capacity This research is expected to be a reference for other faculties to develop education by Implemen ICT in learning.

B. Problem Formulation

Based on the background of the problem described above, the formulation of the problem proposed in this study is "How is the Implementation of Information and Communication Technology in Faculty of Islamic Education, Jakarta Islamic University.

C. Theatrical Study

1. The Basic Concept of Information and Communication Technology

The term information and communication technology (ICT) emerged after a combination of computer technology (both hardware and software) in the mid-20th century. Information and communication technology is needed in human life. ICT according to Adeyemo (2010) is defined as a set of tools and sources of technology used to communicate, create, disseminate, store and manage: information.

According to Custin (2002), Information technology includes everything related to the process, use as a tool, manipulation, and management of information. While communication technology is everything related to the use of tools to process and transfer data from one device to another.

Furthermore, Munir defined computers as advances in advanced-level multimedia technology, even becoming an unusual characteristic that was neglected in the whole life of modernization and acceleration of the present and the future. With educational technology, it can make students more independent, accelerate

mastery and clarify material. With the application of educational technology, students can progress in mastering teaching materials, to choose the pace of work, to repeat the material that is not sufficiently clear, that after tests get results and track their progress.

The views of the experts above: provide a diverse understanding of ICT. Istiningsih defines ICT in general are all technologies related to retrieval, collection, processing, and presentation of information.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that ICT is a technology related to retrieval, collection, processing, storage, dissemination, and presentation of information that is used to facilitate human tasks in carrying out daily life activities. The Impact of using ICTs in learning activities is an important tool in the world today. The use of ICTs provides opportunities for students to learn in various ways and in several spaces. Students can make learning fun and enjoyable which might suggest more on task behavior and better conceptual understanding. The use of ICT by students can make learning more enjoyable this can be seen when giving assignments, behaviors and conceptual understanding of students becomes better. In addition, when students utilize ICT in learning, it directly impacts on increasing motivation because they are directly involved.

2. Use of ICT as a Learning Media

Information processing and distribution through telecommunication networks opens up many opportunities to be utilized in various fields of human life, computers allow students to learn according to their speed and ability. Understanding the material being aired, computers can combine color, music and animated graphics, including one of them making animated simulations as learning media. In line with that began to emerge a variety of jargon beginning with e, ranging from e-books, e-learning, e-laboratory, e-education, and e-library. The prefix e means electronics which is implicitly interpreted based on digital electronics technology.

As explained above, the application of ICT in learning requires adequate skills. Some educators may have very broad knowledge about the teaching material they are teaching, but it is also possible for teachers not be able to convey information in an

innovative and fun way. Therefore, the principal as a leader has consideration in order to improve the quality of the educator.

Using computers in teaching teaches students to think critically, computer is a challenge in skill development. This is in accordance with Gelze's findings that to solve many problems we are helped by new computer with modem programs.

As a learning media, the role of computers is one of the major resources in implementing learning programs in university, through computer training students can run application programs that are also supported by other supporting facilities currently developing, namely the internet. With the internet, students can access information needed in the context of self-development.

Furthermore, the provision of learning materials is done by utilizing high-tech engineering, such as the use of satellites, television, radio or telephone, teleconferences for remote programs such as computer assisted instruction. The initiative to organize educational radio broadcasts and educational television is an effort to disseminate information to educational units spread throughout the archipelago. This is a manifestation of awareness to optimize the use of technology in helping the community learning process.

Internet-based learning allows learning to be synchronized with the main advantages that learners and facilitators do not have to be in the same place. The use of video conference technology that is run using Internet technology allows learners to be anywhere as long as it is connected to a computer network. In addition to such superior applications, several other simpler and less expensive opportunities can also be developed in line with the advancement of ICT today. Furthermore, at the level of implementation, educational technology in solving problems of education and learning

D. Research Methods and Procedures

This study used descriptive-qualitative techniques, then data collection in qualitative research is carried out by: (1) natural conditions, (2) primary and secondary data sources, and (3) more data collection techniques on participant observation, interviews, and documentation .

E. Data Analysis Procedure

Data analysis is the process of searching for and organizing systematically transcripts of interviews, field notes and other materials that have been collected by researchers to increase the understanding of researchers

F. Research Results

1. Planning of Learning with ICT

Based on the results of the interview, it can be explained that before the teacher carries out the study, first he conducts curriculum analysis, prepares instructional objectives, forms of activities directed towards achieving the expected goals, and plans for evaluation. In determining the core objectives, the three domains are cognitive, affective and psychomotor. The cognitive domain discusses learning objectives relating to mental processes that start from the lowest level of knowledge to the highest level of knowledge, evaluation. Affective domains include attitudes, interest values, interests and social feelings. The psychomotor domain relates to manual psychomotor skills

2. Implementation of Learning with ICT

Data from the results of this study provide an explanation of the strategy of actively that involving students. Computers forever can not be said to be able to arouse passion for students learning. Computers also sometimes provide confusion when they are unable to provide detailed information about the material being studied. Therefore, the application of the right strategy should be adjusted to the content and instructional objectives to be achieved. This has an impact on creating focus in the learning process. Likewise, the teacher can use a different combination of strategies.

3. Evaluation of learning E with ICT

At the evaluation stage, an assessment is carried out to determine the quality of learning. The assessment is based on the

aspects to be assessed: cognitive, affective and psychomotor. Assessment is all ways to obtain data about individuals. The assessment system carried out by teachers is a scoring system that aims to improve or follow up on learning outcomes, namely through the translation of lessons from basic competencies. The connection with how to conduct an assessment is obtained from the results of interviews with several teachers as follows;

The data obtained from the interview results are reinforced by observational data, in which Faculty of Islamic Education looks to have used a computer as a tool that facilitates the implementation of activities in learning, almost every classroom has an LCD projector, all teachers have laptops, and most students already have their own laptops, for students who don't have, they can use computers in the laboratory room.

Data from the observations and interviews were reinforced by the results of documentation where in several important documents were obtained related to the application of ICT in this faculty, the documents included photographs of students' learning activities using computers, documents on ICT facilities and infrastructure of this faculty.

G. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The application of ICT in Faculty of Islamic Education is motivated by the demands and needs of the cottage for learning, administration, and the need for soft and hard skills training.

2. The process of planning, implementing, and evaluating the use of ICT in Faculty of Islamic Education is carried out through: a) Meetings involving experts in reviewing the strengths and weaknesses of computer use. b) When using ICT, the approach used is by reviewing the curriculum which then prepares learning scenarios tailored to the steps of activities that are integrated with ICT. c) When carrying out learning using a computer the Faculty of Islamic Education also supervises both special officers and the dean about what the student accesses.

3. The forms of application and the process of integrating ICT in Faculty of Islamic Education include learning aids. Every students holds one computer and each teacher one laptop and in each classroom there is an LCD projector. While the process of integrating ICT into learning activities is carried out by: (a) providing training for teachers to make power points, processing data with Microsoft Exel. (b) Each classroom is facilitated with an LCD projector and sound.. (c) Approach to learning using a software approach, in schools we have interactive CDs, such as learning CDs in English, Arabic,. (e) Evaluation of the use of ICT by teachers is conducted once a month through open discussions with the teacher council.

4. The distinctive characteristics of the use of ICT in Faculty of Islamic Education are compared to other institutions: (a) The motto that is owned is doing something not halfway, doing it the best way. (B) Another distinctive characteristic especially for teachers is allow and tolerate errors and damages done by students when learning and using ICT tools for learning purposes, (c) And the characteristics that are directly related to the religious aspects are a motto of "good, beautiful,

beneficial, prosperous and prosperous" ICT here is positioned on the word "useful "

5. The benefits of using ICT for schools, teachers, students include: a) students already has insights, both national and international. b) Studenvtsare easier and more flexible in learning, because the material in the form of e-book is all already on the laptop or iPad. c) For teachers there are also many who can already make applications for learning purposes. d) Processing administration more quickly and accurately. e) students are very excited when learning to use a laptop. f) Sources of learning for students are wider g) In the field of journalism, the santri have begun to sharpen their writing skills as well as the ability to type on computers.

6. Constraints faced in the application of ICT in Faculty of Islamic Education include: a) Electricity is still low still power deficit, b) Bottle next when using Server / PC Client. c) When using iPad constraints in terms of expensive program prices. d) Lack of government support that is not ready nationally. f) students often forget the time when they hold a laptop or iPad.

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